

**PEDAGOGICAL AND INNOVATIVE FOUNDATIONS FOR IMPROVING THE
QUALITY OF EDUCATION IN NON-STATE EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS
(ON THE EXAMPLE OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION)**

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Abstract: This article discusses the issues of education, namely, the work carried out in the field of preschool education, non-state preschool education, measures of the head of state in the field of preschool education, non-state preschool education, decisions taken, the degree of attention of the educator to the pupil, the role and use of advanced pedagogical technologies in the educational process, non-state preschool education and preschool state-registered education is about the differences and advantages of educational institutions.

Keywords: Preschool education, non-state preschool education, innovative technologies, pedagogical technologies, Material and technical base, private partnership.

**ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ОСНОВЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ
КАЧЕСТВА ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В НЕГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ
УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯХ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ)**

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы образования, а именно, работа, проводимая в сфере дошкольного образования, негосударственное дошкольное образование, меры главы государства в области дошкольного образования, негосударственное дошкольное образование, принятые решения, степень внимания воспитателя к ученику, роль и использование передовых педагогических технологий в образовательном процессе, негосударственное дошкольное образование и дошкольное образование, зарегистрированное государством, - об отличиях и преимуществах образовательных учреждений.

Ключевые слова: дошкольное образование, негосударственное дошкольное образование, инновационные технологии, педагогические технологии, материально-техническая база, частное партнерство.

**NODAVLAT TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA TA'LIM SIFATINI OSHIRISHNING
PEDAGOGIK VA INNOVATSION ASOSLARI
(MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM MISOLIDA)**

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada ta'lim masalalari, ya'ni maktabgacha ta'lim sohasida olib borilayotgan ishlar, nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim, davlat rahbarining maktabgacha ta'lim sohasidagi chora-tadbirlari, nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim, qabul qilingan qarorlar, o'qituvchining diqqat darajasi, ta'lim jarayonida ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalarning roli va ulardan foydalanish, nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim va maktabgacha ta'lim davlat tomonidan ro'yxatdan o'tgan ta'lim-ta'lim muassasalarining farqlari va afzalliklari tadqiq etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Maktabgacha ta'lim, nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim, innovatsion texnologiyalar, pedagogik texnologiyalar, moddiy-texnik baza, xususiy sheriklik.

INTRODUCTION

Preschool education is the ancestral homeland, the foundation, the foundation of continuing education. Focusing on this, we should pay a lot of attention to preschool education. A lot of work is currently being done in this direction.

The work recognized by the head of our state to cover children aged 3 to 7 years with preschool education, paying great attention to their upbringing is of great importance.

A.Avloni said, education-upbringing is a matter of life and death for us. The main task of preschool education is to expand the state and non-state network of preschool educational institutions, strengthen the material and technical base, provide qualified personnel, expand the coverage of children with preschool education, radically positive change in the quality of intellectual, spiritual, aesthetic, physical development and preparation of children for school through the use of modern educational programs and technologies in the educational process.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The importance of new methodological developments and innovative technologies in improving the quality of education is very great. The main basis of training is the method. Let's say the material and technical base in preschool education is high, but all the actions performed are useless if the educator does not work with children, does not teach them daily classes.

The main agenda was the provision of highly qualified personnel who form the most necessary life concepts and skills in pupils, the development of advanced pedagogical methods in this area, the creation of new teaching aids. In this regard, the state educational program of the preschool educational institution of the Republic of Uzbekistan "The first step" (ilk qadam) has been adopted. In accordance with this program, preschool teachers freely teach children new information through educational activities conducted in a playful way in activity centers.

What is the difference between a state preschool and a non-state preschool?

Previously, people were a little nervous when they said that this was a private kindergarten or a non-state preschool. The reason was that the difference between their cost was large, only financially secure families could send their children to a non-state educational institution. To date, the ongoing work on expanding the network of non-state preschool institutions has led to a sharp increase in the number of non-state preschool institutions.

The large-scale reforms carried out in recent years in all spheres have also led to huge changes in the field of education, especially in preschool education. A number of innovations have been achieved in the provision of non-governmental educational services, the development and implementation of an effective mechanism of public-private partnership, as well as the study and application of advanced foreign experience in this area.

Until recently, the entrepreneur believed that the difficulty of obtaining a license for non-governmental services has disappeared today.

Thanks to the clear implementation of the instructions of the relevant ministries and departments in this matter, this problem has found its solution. Resolution of September 15, 2017 "On measures for the further development of activities for the provision of non-state educational services " entailed significant changes in the field of non-state education.

At the moment, the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in every educational process is a requirement of the time. Innovative pedagogical technology is the structure of the organization of the educational process in a modern style, a consistent method of creating and implementing educational processes in technology and the human factor, by means of their joint actions aimed at improving the forms of education, providing a sharp increase in the required level and quality of education and meeting the requirements of rapidly developing scientific and technological progress.

Innovative education creates an opportunity for the student to create a new idea, new rules, progressive ideas created by others, natural acceptance of rules, the formation of competencies.

The main goal of innovative pedagogical technologies is to achieve the commonality of the educator and the pupil, to interest the pupil in science, to teach him to use the knowledge being studied, to develop his giftedness taking into account his interests.

So, what is the work on the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in preschool education, in particular, in non-state preschool institutions?

What is the advantage of non-state preschool institutions over state preschool institutions?

There is relative freedom in a non-state preschool institution.

Develops the curriculum itself.

Small minority groups may be formed, taking into account the nature, age, and interests of children. This, in turn, plays an important role in mastering the level of transferred knowledge, concepts and skills.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Currently, there is a growing interest and attention in the field of education to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies, their application in the educational process. Until now, the teacher shares ready-made knowledge with the student. Did not go beyond its limits on the basis of the installed formwork.

If we talk about this from the point of view of new innovative pedagogical technologies used in preschool education, especially in the process of educating and training pupils in the activities of non-state preschool educational institutions, then efforts aimed at ensuring that children grow up as mature people in the future, relying on foreign experience, guided by the principles of public-private partnership are especially significant. Therefore, at present, along with state preschool institutions, the demand for non-state preschool institutions is growing.

Educational hours spent in non-state preschool educational institutions using computers, smart TVs, the use of non-traditional methods, a trip in the bosom of wildlife to familiarize children with nature, for example, in the process of picking fruits, where fruits grow, when they ripen, what color the fruit is, or if we take the process of caring for plants, which of them to what extent to water the plant, how long it sprouts, to conduct such classes as how many centimeters it grows for what time of year; what nature looks like at what time of the year, what natural phenomena occur – all this the child sees, feels with his own eyes.

In the process of drawing, making manual labor, the child is given freedom, is given the opportunity to act freely in accordance with his abilities, imagination, pay attention to his talents, develop abilities, doing more of his business, depending on the interests and abilities of each child;

An effective result gives students the opportunity to learn 2 or more languages, the use of innovative pedagogical technologies, advanced foreign experience in the process of language learning, since in the same process children gain knowledge about the language of the country whose language is being studied with the help of technology cartoons and fairy tales shown in their native language play an important role in the speech development of children.

CONCLUSIONS

Thus, while the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in education generally raises the picture of education, innovative technologies promote educational progress forward. The development and future of each state is determined by the degree of development of its education system.

The basis and foundation of education is primarily preschool education. This shows that we must first focus on preschool education.

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